

Studies on Complex Compounds of Chromium(III) with Substituted Thiosemicarbazides

U. N. PANDEY

Department of Chemistry, Samastipur College, Samastipur.

Manuscript received 3 January 1977, revised 17 November 1977, accepted 14 March 1978

Four complex compounds of Cr(III) of the formula $[\text{Cr L}_3]$ with *p*-substituted benzaldehydethiosemicarbazone(L), *p*-(X).C₆H₄.CH : N.NH.CS.NH₂ (X=NO₂, Cl, NH₂ and OCH₃) have been prepared and characterised. The structures of these paramagnetic and octahedral complexes have been established on the basis of their elemental analysis, ir, uv and magnetic moment values.

COMPLEXES of trivalent chromium with nitrogen sulphur containing ligands such as substituted thiosemicarbazides are unknown. The present communication reports four Cr(III) complexes, namely, Tris *p*-nitrobenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone Cr(III), Tris *p*-chlorobenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone Cr(III) and Tris *p*-methoxybenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone Cr(III).

Experimental

Ligands : *P*-Nitrobenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone was prepared by dissolving 1 gm. *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde in acetone and treated with a solution of thiosemicarbazide hydrochloride in equimolecular quantity in distilled water. Yellow precipitate was obtained when shaken vigorously but by the same process a pale yellow precipitate of *p*-chlorobenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone was obtained when shaken only for a few minutes.

In the case of *p*-aminobenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone a liquid layer was obtained after refluxing on waterbath for about an hour, the liquid layer extracted with ether and solidified by distilling off ether. But the heavy liquid layer obtained in the case of *p*-methoxybenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone was separated by means of a separating funnel and solidified by evaporation on a waterbath.

Complexes : 10 c.c. of 1 p.c. solution of chromium sulphate was treated with the ligand solution prepared by dissolving equimolecular quantity of the ligand in acetone, refluxed on waterbath for about 15 minutes and allowed to cool at room temperature. This solution was then made neutral by adding a very dilute solution of ammonia. It was then allowed to stand for an hour, filtered and washed with distilled water. The fine crystals so separated was recrystallised in acetone and dried in air.

(i) Found : Cr, 7.18% ; N, 23.00% ; C, 39.84% ; H, 2.90% ;

Calcd. for $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})_3]$: Cr, 7.20% ;

N, 23.28% ; C, 39.94% ; H, 2.93%.

(ii) Found : Cr, 7.51% ; N, 18.05% ; C, 41.57% ; H, 2.90% ;

Calcd. for $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{ClS})_3]$: Cr, 7.53% ; N, 18.27% ; C, 41.77% ; H, 3.06%.

(iii) Found : Cr, 8.20% ; N, 26.45% ; C, 45.60% ; H, 4.00% ;

Calcd. for $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_4\text{S})_3]$: Cr, 8.23% ; N, 26.60% ; C, 45.62% ; H, 4.30%.

(iv) Found : Cr, 7.64% ; N, 18.60% ; C, 47.70% ; H, 4.33% ;

Calcd. for $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{OS})_3]$: Cr, 7.68% ; N, 18.62% ; C, 47.91% ; H, 4.43%.

All the four Cr(III) complexes are soluble in acetone and are stable upto 130°.

Results and Discussion

Measurement of magnetic susceptibility by Gouy's method (Found $\mu_B = 3.89$ B.M., expected $\mu_B = 3.87$ B.M.) indicated that the complexes contain three unpaired electrons.

Electronic absorption spectral measurement of these complexes in acetone showed three absorption bands, namely, at 15000 cm⁻¹, 23500 cm⁻¹ and 35000 cm⁻¹ in the case of Tris *p*-chlorobenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone Cr(III) and at 15020 cm⁻¹, 23500 cm⁻¹ and 34900 cm⁻¹ in the case of Tris *p*-methoxybenzaldehydethiosemicarbazone Cr(III). From the Orgel diagram of

